

Imprisoning the Enemies of France. A Historical Overview on French Internment Camps in the First Half of the Twentieth Century

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This paper examines the concentration and internment camps installed in France during the First and Second World Wars. While both periods' concentration system played a significant role in the historical and wartime events of the twentieth century, concentration camps are commonly associated with the German "Final Solution", nonetheless, they already existed in France before that. The purpose of these camps was not extermination, but rather the imprisonment of civilians perceived as a threat during conflicts. The history of concentration camps dates back further than World War II or French authorities installing them during World War I up until the 19th century. Throughout the First World War, internment camps were used from the beginning of the war until 1920, while during World War II from 1938 to 1946, serving various functions. These camps held a diverse range of individuals, including Austro-Germans, Austro-Hungarians, Alsatian-Lorrains, Spanish, resistance fighters, Gypsies, Jews, Germans, Freemasons, Communists, etc. The camps in France varied in their populations, interned women, children, men, soldiers, elderly individuals. This paper aims to provide a comprehensive overview of the different types of concentration and internment camps established in France during this turbulent period. The article summarises these two periods relying on two fundamental researchers in this topic: Jean-Claude Farcy and Denis Peschanski.

[French Concentration Camps; French Internment Camps; First World War; Second World War; Internment Systems; Undesirable Individuals]

Introduction

Among the historical and wartime events of the twentieth century, we must not forget the installation of *concentration camps* or *internment camps*. Although concentration camps are now understood as the "Final

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Solution” created by the Germans, they also referred to the French internment camps before that. The purpose of these camps was not a carefully planned extermination, but the imprisonment of civilians who meant a threat to the country: women, children and men, for the duration of a conflict.

However, it is also important to note that the history of the first existing concentration camps goes back much further, while in France, the local authorities installed them from the outbreak of the First World War, then known as *concentration camps*. During this period of the war, foreigners or suspected spies, men who could be mobilised, people from Alsace-Lorraine, Austro-Germans, prostitutes, etc. were interned. There were also various types of camps, whether for families, notables, prostitutes or priests.

As for the Second World War, according to historian Denis Peschanski, the use of internment camps lasted from 1938 to 1946. The internment camps set up during this period can be divided into four main periods according to their function: *emergency* (1938–1940), *exclusion* (1940–1942), *deportation* (1942–1944) and again *emergency* (1944–1946). During this period, a more diverse range of civilians were interned than during the First World War. The operation of the camps began with the mass exodus of Spaniards and continued with the internment of French resistance fighters, Gypsies, Jews, Germans, Freemasons, Communists, etc. There were different uses of camps in the north and south of France: some where only women and children were imprisoned; others where only men; soldiers; the elderly; Jews; resistance fighters or people from Spain were concentrated.

In this paper, therefore, our purpose is to clarify the types of concentration camps, to precise definition of the terms, also to realise a more global overview of the internment camps set up in France in the first half of the twentieth century including the internees’ characteristics (gender and age), the functioning of these camps and several examples of them from each period.

Types of Concentration Camps

French internment camps are often referred to as French concentration camps in literary works in different languages and culture, as well as several times in historical works on the subject. However, it would be appropriate for us to clarify the historical background of this term, given that since the creation of the German concentration camps, reference is

often made to premeditated and meticulously calculated annihilation; not all concentration systems are the same, and all have their own characteristics.² Nevertheless, we should not ignore the fact that these concentration camps have the same consequences, including the appearance of “*concentration, segregation, the disappearance of the most fundamental rights, the deterioration of survival conditions ranging from programmed extermination to random probability.*”³

Depending on the period, these notions have different meanings and function, differing widely depending on the country and its culture. Nonetheless, the first time that the notion *concentrationnaire* in French (in English we refer in this case to concentration camps) was used by David Rousset, a French writer and political activist.⁴ Rousset survived two extermination camps: Neuengamme and Buchenwald and then wrote his testimonial accounts of life in the Nazi concentration camps. From its publication in 1946 by Éditions du Pavois, this notion began to indicate these camps created by the German authorities which organised the final solution for the inmates, which is why these terms are regularly mixed up since these events and that we must distinguish between the terms.

The first real concentration camps were set up by a Spanish general, Valeriano Weyler y Nicolau, in Cuba during the Cuban War of Independence of 1895–1898, as well as by the British during the Boer Wars and by the Germans in present-day Namibia.⁵ Besides these, during the History, there were several other internment or concentration camps established, such as the Soviet Gulag, the Chinese Laogai, Francisco Franco’s camps, so much more which are not to be listed in this work yet.

Only to have a broader picture of these incarceration systems and to be able to compare to those created in France, we wish to see how these in different countries and cultures functioned. First of all, the already mentioned Spanish general, Valeriano Weyler y Nicolau demanded the

² J. SÁNCHEZ ZAPATERO, La literatura concentracionaria: universalidad, representación y memoria, in: *Vegueta. Anuario de la Facultad de Geografía e Historia*, 19, 2019, pp. 431–455.

³ J. M. NAHARRO-CALDERÓN, *Entre alambradas y exilios. Sangrías de las Españas y terapias de Vichy*, Madrid 2017, pp. 87–88.

⁴ Y. HAMEL, Le sport concentrationnaire: David Rousset, Georges Perec, in: *Des mots et des muscles! Représentations des pratiques sportives*, s. l. 2005, pp. 231–250.

⁵ A. BECKER, La genèse des camps de concentration: Cuba, la guerre des Boers, la grande guerre de 1896 aux années vingt, in: *Revue d’Histoire de la Shoah*, 189, 2008, pp. 101–129.

imprisonment of civil people to avoid the Cuban insurrection in 1896 in guarded areas. These imprisoned rebels were mainly those who were established by the colonial authorities and would be concentrated to these camps to cease the war caused by immigration and economic crisis. Therefore, the general's plan was not exterminating the civilian population, but to not aggravating the situation in Cuba. The local authorities contributed to select the areas of the internees and supply them with food but ended up providing them poorly these basic needs which led to starvation, sickness, dehydration, and death. Due to these consequences, to the tens of thousands of deaths, Jakub Chustecki, from the Warsaw University questions with right the true intention of these camps and affirms that this event is "*a dangerous precedent that would be used in the future.*"⁶

Thus, with only just three years apart, in 1899 the Second Boer War started with the British invasion in the Boer republics. The concentration camps were established at the end of 1900 by the British army in order to protect those Boer families whose male family members could be mobilised, so they were known first as "safety zones", however, their function changed radically in December 1900.⁷ They then served as a kind of motivation for the Boers to end guerrillas, otherwise they would risk the life of their loved ones due to poor conditions. Just like in the Spanish concentration camps in Cuba, they could not organise properly nor the food, nor the places to sleep which resulted also numerous death cases. According to the calculation of Jarosław Żukowski, from June 1901 until December 1901, approximately 14,850 civil people died due to lack of food, water, or to sickness, so, with the increasing number of prisoners from month to month, the rate of fatality grew as well.⁸ While the plan was to not exterminate these civilians, as a consequence of the deficient treatment, circa 18,000–28,000 Boers died indirectly.⁹

Other than that, not only British and Spanish committed this kind of tactic during warfare, but Germans also, first, in Shark Island in Central Namibia. The German colonial forces installed the concentration camp in 1905 to incarcerate Herero and Nama people during the Herero and

⁶ J. CHUSTECKI, Colonial concentration camps in Cuba and South Africa. Characteristics and significance for the evolution of the idea, in: *Świat Idei i Polityki*, 2, 2023, pp. 140–151.

⁷ Ibid.

⁸ Ibid.

⁹ Ibid.

Namaqua Genocide. It closed in April 1907 and left behind 1000–3000 death in the camp. The German colonial administration put in this camp those who survived the genocidal assault to eventually annihilate them by making them overwork, not giving them normal medical treatments, or exposing them to physical abuse.¹⁰

The Gulag, prison camp system in the Soviet Union after 1929, differed in a way that they did not specifically incarcerated ethnics but the entire population. The prisoners had to serve from five to twenty years of hard labour and suffer from starvation, sickness, violence, cold causing 1,6 million civilians to die from 14 million prisoners throughout the years.¹¹ Here we should also mention the Laogai which was based on the Soviet Gulag installed by the Chinese Communist Party so that they could influence 50 million prisoners – of which 20 million died – to accept and support the Party's ideology from 1954.¹²

Besides, near to France, precisely in Spain or in its Spanish Protectorate in Morocco, the dictator Francisco Franco has also installed 298 concentration camps from 18 July 1936. As far as the prisoners are concerned, there were 700,000 Spanish men and women who were interned and thousands of them might have died from hunger, disease, illness. In this case, Franco separated more the inmates, thus homosexuals, the poor, political dissidents and their families, Republican ex-combatants of the People's Army, the Air Force and the Navy, Gypsies, Moroccan separatists, and common prisoners were tortured, beaten up, made to do forced labour, sentenced to accept the present ideology of the government. Franco's military indiscriminately shot these inmates and had no intention to provide food, warm clothing to protect them from the cold, basic hygienic or sanitary conditions. Consequently, it was more like an extermination camp than a concentration or internment camp.¹³

In France, meanwhile, from the early months of the First World War, local authorities set up and ran internment camps, known at the time as concentration camps. They mainly interned men who were at the age of mobilisation, foreigners, suspected spies, Alsatian-Lorrains,

¹⁰ M. ADHIKARI, 'Streams of blood and streams of money': New perspectives on the annihilation of the Herero and Nama peoples of Namibia, 1904-1908, in: *Kronos*, 34, 1, 2008, pp. 303–320.

¹¹ <https://gulaghistory.org/nps/downloads/gulag-curriculum.pdf> [2024-02-07].

¹² <https://laogairesearch.org/museum/what-is-laogai/> [2024-02-07].

¹³ <https://www.loscamposdeconcentraciondefranco.es/index.php> [2024-02-07].

Austro-Germans, etc.¹⁴ As far as the Second World War is concerned, according to French historian Denis Peschanski, this period of internment camps can be divided into four parts: “*the exception (1938–1940), exclusion (1940–1942), deportation (1942–1944), and the exception again (1944–1946)*.”¹⁵ These stages correspond to the internment of various entities, such as Spanish men, women and children, Resistance fighters, Gypsies, Germans, Communists, Jews, etc. In the upcoming chapters, we will study each phase of the French internment camps.

The conclusion for this part might be that in each camp from different years, countries, regimes or culture, the inmates faced almost the same difficulties: barracks with no electricity, no drinking water, insufficient food, underdeveloped sewage networks, strictly limited postal services, makeshift hospitals, cold, forced labour, violence, discrimination and depriving them of their freedom. Every camp had its inhuman conditions for men, women, and children alike.¹⁶

The First Initiatives: French Internment Camps during the First World War

French authorities also followed the example of installing concentration camps for the period of war, however, their purpose differs from one global armed conflict to another, nevertheless, it was never to exterminate just like the Nazis or Franco did. Considering the First World War, creating these concentration camps has never been a question: in political circles, there was unanimity on the need for opening them. Their intention was military, they wanted to defend the country from any danger that might have had occurred, for instance, German spies or men who could have had joined the enemy’s army and interests.¹⁷

During the war, approximately 60,000 foreigners, suspects, undesirables were concentrated in 70 camps. These camps were mainly located in the coastal areas of the West and South-East, in remote locations that were easy to monitor and harder to escape from. The most numerous were reserved for Austro-Germans, especially La Ferté-Macé in the Orne department, region of Normandy, northwestern France which received

¹⁴ J-C. FARCY, Les camps d'internement de la Première Guerre mondiale, in: *Revue Quart Monde*, 232, 2014, pp. 45–50.

¹⁵ D. PESCHANSKI, *Les camps français d'internement (1938–1946)*. Thèse de doctorat d'État en Histoire, Paris 2000, p. 3.

¹⁶ C. LAHARIE, *Camps d'internement français (1939–1945)*, Pau 2020, pp. 29–65.

¹⁷ FARCY, pp. 45–50.

6141 prisoners from February 1915 to May 1919, in each month about 200 new inmates arrived. Furthermore, there were camps in Fleury-en-Bière in the Seine-et-Marne department in the Île-de-France, with 2678 internees from almost the same period, and in Besançon with 5825 Austro-German and French citizens.¹⁸ All these three camps were primarily sorting camps (*camp du triage*), i.e., camps in which they sent everyone, so that they can select who must be sent to concentration (internment) camps, who ought to receive control but could reside at their own place or who could gain back their liberty completely.

The buildings used as internment or concentration camps were rarely in possession of the government, except for the forts and military barracks more and more in the coastal areas, e.g., îles d'Yeu and Noirmoutier, but there were also factories, like fish cannery, rope factory, aircraft canvas factory sometimes with barbed wire to prevent escape.¹⁹ It is important also to note that at the beginning, they did not separate between genders the camps, only in dormitories. This kind of separation started from 21 December 1914, when the French internment camps were mainly reserved for men, because women, children, and elderly were imprisoned when they did not want to be apart from their husband or family, yet they were later sent back to their country.²⁰

Authorities installed special camps as well in 1916 for former legionnaires and internees loyal to France, men from relatively high social class, just like for priests and prostitutes. The same diversity existed for the Alsatian-Lorrains evacuated to guarded depots and free depots (or houses of refuge). Each of these establishments had regulations that varied depending on the population held there. These French concentration camps had a similar regime to that of prisons, except that work, apart from the usual chores (cleaning, cooking), was optional for civilian internees.²¹ The authorities, in addition, did not have enough time nor financial capacities to provide adequate conditions, for this reason, these political prisoners lived in poor material conditions during their detention: unsanitary environment, cold, insufficient and defective food, restrictions on correspondence. Moreover, loads of them did not get financial support, thus could not pay for food in the camps and with

¹⁸ J-C. FARCY, *Les camps de concentration français de la première guerre mondiale (1914–1920)*, Paris 1995, pp. 111–113.

¹⁹ *Ibid.*, pp. 137–138.

²⁰ *Ibid.*, pp. 164–166.

²¹ FARCY, *Les camps d'internement*, pp. 45–50.

the duration of the war and labour shortages, the French government was loose on labour force, therefore, they called on internees to work, mainly on farms. In spite the fact that this was a way to leave the camps, the Austro-Germans denied out of patriotism these measures.²²

The system of concentration camps in this period was far the same as those during the Second World War, but before entering in more details, we shall examine the two principal group of internees in the next two chapters.

Foreigners Without French Nationality

We shall not ignore the fact that when we discuss the historical background of French concentration camps, one of the most fundamental works are from Jean-Claude Farcy, a French historian who worked for the French National Centre for Scientific Research for twenty-nine years. During the first part of our article, we will rely on his results and book intitled *Les camps de concentration français de la première guerre Mondiale (1914–1920)* published in 1995 by Anthropos-Economica.

First of all, when the mobilisation started in France, in August 1914 – there were already more than 3 million mobilised men –,²³ while in parallel, they began to evacuate German and Austro-Hungarian nationals from the Northeast region and the cities of Paris and Lyon. According to a decree of 2 August 1914, these undesirables had two options, whether they left the country freely (within 24 hours), whether they stayed and obtain a residence permit to travel. Nonetheless, very few of them could quit France, since trains or buses would not depart, or if, they were already full, so in September, the evacuation to “refuge centres” or internment camps occurred as well. Most of the residents in France found themselves in these sorting camps which were followed by concentration camps.²⁴

The Ministry of the Interior on 1 September 1914 decided that Austro-Germans must be put under surveillance, thus housed in collective premises, and were authorised to leave the towns or houses if they were *notables*, in other words, people with exceptional treatment, good acquaintanceship. From then on, “special depots” were set up for these people of a rather high social class and became hostages likely to be exchanged with Germany.²⁵

²² Ibid.

²³ The order was declared on this day, but the mobilisation applied to the 2 August.

J. SZIJJ, *Magyarország az első világháborúban. Lexikon A–Zs*, Budapest 200, p. 800.

²⁴ A. KUNCZ, *Fekete kolostor. Feljegyzések a francia internáltságból*, Budapest 1975, p. 20.

²⁵ FARCY, *Les camps de concentration français*, pp. 166–177.

On the other hand, the main reason for trying to practice strict discipline was because of men who could be mobilised and enrolled into the enemy's armies, so France started to establish coastal camps from 12 September, internment these foreign nationals. A circular dated 15 September prescribed the evacuation of all Austro-Germans without exception, even those with a residence permit, to concentration camps. Another circular dated 1st of October specified that this measure applied also to women, children and the elderly people who were waiting for the evacuation to Switzerland. Only those foreigners whose Francophile feelings seemed assured would gain their liberty, either because they belonged to national minorities oppressed in the Austrian Empire (Poles, Czechs, Serbs), or because they had been or had joined the French army, more precisely the French Foreign Legion. These harmless and loyal citizens only stayed in the camps for a few months, until they could check their commitment to France.²⁶

The internment measures continued throughout the conflict and not only Austro-Germans, but Austro-Hungarians were also incarcerated together with more and more families. For instance, a former convent of Ursulines housed in 1915 approximately four hundred Austro-Germans from whom about fifty were women and children. Although, there was a re-organisation and in 1916, they installed a camp in the Morbihan department, in the Kerlois castle, which would be one of the biggest camps in this department with the capacity of sheltering four hundred and fifty people but would have to host around eight hundred internees. In the case of the medieval town in the region of Pays de la Loire, Western France, Guérande, we also have information about the number of inmates from November 1918. Among men, Farcy found that there were seventy-one Germans, ninety-two Austrians, twenty-two Hungarians and eleven Ottomans. From the same nationalities, there were eighteen German women, eleven German children, twelve Austrian women, eighteen Austrian children, seven Hungarian women, twelve Hungarian children and three Ottoman women and five Ottoman children. From these numbers, we can see that the presence of families was less common due to repatriation of them in 1914. The separation of genders, however, in these camps was in fact strict. Women with their children and men received different rooms and could see their kids when the commandment of the camp allowed them, more precisely, two or three times a day during mainly four hours a day in the courtyard.²⁷

²⁶ FARCY, *Les camps d'internement*, pp. 45–50.

²⁷ FARCY, *Les camps de concentration français*, pp. 166–168.

As far as the *notables* are concerned, they were mostly retailers, teachers, students, marine officers, artists interned in Noirmoutier, île d'Yeu or the hotel of Carnac in Morbihan. In their case, the government had no financial responsibility since the notables had enough money to pay for the hotel which took care of the meals during their stay. The Hôtel de la Plage in Carnac hosted more than a hundred people who paid six to eight francs. They could go on a walk every day from seven in the morning until seven in the evening but was prohibited for them to talk with the hotel employees.²⁸

The practice of interning enemy nationals was closely linked to the conduct of the war, thus those whose family members served in the military as foreigners were excluded from exchanges of civilian internees between belligerents, that's the reason why women and kids could be repatriated through or to another country. The internment continued even after the armistice, for refugees or released internees from Germany or for Russians, soldiers in the Red Army and representatives of the Bolshevik authorities.²⁹

Suspects and Undesirables with French Nationality

Among those who did not have French nationality, there were also civilians in the camps who have received the citizenship years ago but were still imprisoned. The decision, whether they must be incarcerated or set free, was made by a Classification Commission created in November 1914 in France and what caused the suspicion for the French authorities were mainly those Alsatians who would reside in France but had not opted for French nationality only after 1871. Therefore, this sorting commission divided into three categories their behaviour towards Alsatian-Lorrains. First, they approved "pure Alsatians", being recognised completely as French, who would be given tricolour cards which represented their liberty, then several thousand of them would obtain a "white card" judging them to have dubious attitude, so they were imprisoned in *surveillance camps*. While those who were Austro-Germans were sent to *suspect detention centres* together with those who had relatives in the German army. Besides, other problems appeared as well, because Alsatians who received the tricolour card had difficulties to find work, so the authorities thought that the right solution would be to send them in *open camps*. Consequently,

²⁸ Ibid., pp. 169–173.

²⁹ Ibid., pp. 166–180.

there were principally and initially two types of camps: those that were monitored or unrestricted.³⁰

Regarding the surveillance camps, in 1916, there were four of them functioning in Luçon in the Vendée department, in Bouches-du-Rhône department and Saint-Maximin in the Var department. The directors of these camps must have provided enough cloths; underwear, shoes; bed for women, children, and elderly; sufficient food (bread, meat, and vegetables), must have changed frequently the straw; moreover, they must have let them out to go to work. Nevertheless, they could not undertake any foreign work, especially in the Red Cross or in the German government. The inmates were not satisfied with how the authorities and directors of these camps wanted to manipulate them, several of them (men who were already fifty-five years old or disabled, women and children) wanted to be repatriated, so they received the permission or those who chose to stay in France received the tricolour card. Because of this, from 1917, these camps were transformed into internment camps for men who could be still mobilised.³¹

As far as the unrestricted camps are concerned, they did not differ much from the surveillance camps that transformed into internment camps, except that they became a sort of refugee camp for Alsatians who were evacuated long ago from the occupied zone and from German Alsace, as well as for Alsatians who wanted to return to Alsace to their families. On the contrary, suspect detention centres or camps were more important regarding the number of internees. There were more restrictions concerning the food, the correspondence, the amount of money they would have. For instance, the Précigné camp in the Sarthe department was installed in 1914 and hosted immediately 664 internees, while by the end of October 1919, they counted 2123 people. Among them the most numerous were Belgians, Russians, Alsatians and until 1917 we could observe the presence of women without children that also caused disciplinary problems. In total, 279 Belgian and Russian women will then be separated and sent to other camps. The Précigné camp would be closed in 1919, thus this was one of the last evacuated camps.³²

Lastly, we should not ignore the two specific camps in the history of internment during World War I. One of them is the Langonnet camp

³⁰ *Ibid.*, p. 180.

³¹ *Ibid.*, pp. 180–181.

³² *Ibid.*, pp. 185–188.

for Austro-German priests. This camp was situated in the Morbihan department and was an abbey that served in that period as an option for separating non-ecclesiastic people from clergyman. For this internment camp, the same restrictions applied, e.g., they could not receive visitors and their correspondence with other people were also monitored and reduced to certain quantity of times. If any orders were disobeyed, the clergymen were sent to “normal” concentration camps where people with no higher position were imprisoned. According to Jean-Claude Farcy, not all priests were placed in this camp, there were several others (Catholics and Protestants as well) who were in a camp in Guérande.³³

Another particular camp was the Kergroès camp where prostitutes were interned in a hotel. The aim of the incarceration of prostitutes was to protect France from any spying and men from becoming infected with any illness which would have made them unable to fight.³⁴ These women had to pay 1,25 franc per day, and it was allowed for them to go on a walk within a fixed distance, more precisely in one kilometre radius. They also had the possibility to swim in the sea but only with cloths on. Furthermore, the director of the camp and the hotel made special rules, for instance, throwing dirty water; receiving visitors; damaging the hotel’s equipment, walls, or tiles. Some of these women engaging in sexual activity for payment did not respect these rules and ended up in courts for having physical relationship with the enemy’s soldiers or were convicted of drunkenness. The guards of the hotel could not cope with the behaviour of these women, thus many of them quit this camp which resulted its closure in 1915. Women who were still imprisoned at that time were placed in brothels or found them other work.³⁵

As we could observe, there was not a wide range of internees during the First World War, at least not as wide as it would be throughout the Second World War. In the upcoming chapters, our purpose is to confirm this statement and to outline the different stages of this internment system.

The Second Initiatives: French Internment Camps during the Second World War

As we mentioned in the chapter of the First World War period, Jean-Claude Farcy was the researcher who wrote about this concentration camp system,

³³ Ibid., pp. 193–194.

³⁴ FARCY, *Les camps d'internement*, pp. 47–48

³⁵ FARCY, *Les camps de concentration français*, pp. 194–195.

but for the French internment camps during the Second World War, the expert is Denis Peschanski, himself also a French historian who works for the French National Centre for Scientific Research. Denis Peschanski observes four main period of internment camps from 1938 to 1946 in his opus intitled *La France des camps. L'internement 1938–1946*. He details and divides this way: “*exception (1938–1940), exclusion (1940–1942), deportation (1942–1944), and the exception again (1944–1946)*.”³⁶ As we can see, each period lasted two years and had its own public thought to be undesirable and danger to the French Government. Besides Denis Peschanski, we should also mention Claude Laharie, a French historian who is a retired teacher at Lycée Louis Barthou and University of Pau. He published several works on the war and the Gurs camp which shall be considered to be references on these subjects. He resumes in his oeuvre *Camps d'internement français (1939–1945)* almost the same way the episodes of internment adding a period of *Debaacle Camps (June July 1940)* and a period of *Liberation and Epuration Camps (1940–1944)*. With the help of these two important works, we would like to summarise this period.

The beginning of the system of internment camp touches the era of the fading Third Republic and the impromptu internment measures of the 1930s, of which the main victims were foreigners likely to threaten French identity. If we go back in time, as early as February 1937, because of Franco's offensive on Malaga, the French ambassador already predicted several tens of thousands of potential refugees.³⁷ Two years later, on 26 January 1939, more and more requests arrived from the Republicans to open accommodation centres to take in around 150,000 women, children, and elderly people in France. In response to this request, Édouard Daladier, the French Minister of Foreign Affairs, offered to take in the refugees in an area bordering Spanish territory. Denis Peschanski argues that, in taking this step, the French authorities chose to bury their heads in the sand, given that “*they refused to direct the refugees towards military camps, to provide military health facilities and to keep coherent military units in the camps*”, the result of which was chaos.³⁸ All in all, 450,000 Spaniards crossed the border, 350,000 of whom were confined to camps.³⁹ Therefore, this historical event has launched the reopening or creating new internment camps all around France.

³⁶ PESCHANSKI, p. 3.

³⁷ Ibid., p. 41.

³⁸ Ibid.

³⁹ LAHARIE, p. 29.

In terms of their characteristics and functions, for example, in the beginning, six specialised camps were identified, in particular for the elderly in Bram, in the Aude department; for the Catalans in Agde, in the Hérault department and Rivesaltes (Pyrénées-Orientales). In addition, two camps were set up for “*specialised workers to be reclassified in the French economy*” in Septfonds (Tarn-et-Garonne) and Le Vernet (Ariège), as well as for Basques in Gurs (Basses-Pyrénées). Each of these camps housed between 15 and 18,000 people.⁴⁰ These characteristics of camps only applied to the first episode of internment camps. There were about two hundred camps installed throughout the World War II, imprisoning around 600,000 different nationalities, individuals with not the same ideologies or religion without knowing the duration of their incarceration. Among them, we recognise Spanish, communists from different nations, Jews, Tziganes, German, Anglo-Saxons, etc.⁴¹ The rigor and unpreparedness were really similar to the First World War’s, in the sense that they did not have enough time nor financial capacities to provide adequate conditions, thus, these political prisoners experienced the poor material conditions during their detention: improvised camps and sleeping place, unsanitary conditions, cold, insufficient and defective food, restrictions and censorship on correspondence, confiscation of documents and property et cetera.⁴² In the upcoming chapters, we will observe and describe some of the functioning and characteristics some of fundamental camps during this period.

The Period of Spanish Republican Refugees: The Politic of Exception

The first camps from World War II, as we have already mentioned, covers the period of the late Third Republic which introduced the *politic of exception*, in other words, when camps must have been created immediately to solve a massif immigration problem (the consequences of *Retirada*) from Spain to France. However, they were not only imprisoned because France could not provide them enough shelter, but also because they were communists (*hordes rouges*) of which France was afraid that the people with opposing the ideology of Francisco Franco would quasi “invade” the whole country.⁴³

⁴⁰ PESCHANSKI, p. 54.

⁴¹ Ibid., p. 3.

⁴² Ibid., p. 30.

⁴³ LAHARIE, p. 30.

Spanish Republican would already start to flee to France from February 1937, the year when Franco's offensive on Malaga happened, and when the French ambassador was already predicting tens of thousands of potential refugees. However, French authorities only installed reception centres in March 1938 after another Franco's offensive in Aragon. Almost a year after, on 26 January 1939, the French Minister of Foreign Affairs received more requests from the Republicans in order to open more shelters for 150,000 women, children and elderly escaping to France, but the Minister of Foreign Affairs would not take action because he had the intention to install shelters in a neutral border zone on a Spanish territory, thus creating a chaos.⁴⁴ Spanish would arrive on foot to France through the Pyrenees and would have to obey at the entrance in France strict gendarmes who would separate families, putting women, children and men in different camps.

French leaders were totally surprised by the scale of the exodus of 465,000 Spanish who crossed the border: 350,000 of them were "welcomed" in improvised camps, most of them would flee to Latin America, so there were two types of camps: sorting camps to help these refugees to get to Ibero-America and camps sometimes referred to as "concentration camps" but would mean definitely French internment camps.⁴⁵

The first internment camp that the French authorities opened was situated in Argèles-sur-Mer in the Pyrénées-Orientales department, Southern France. The camp was located in a vast area bordering the sea, surrounded by barbed wire, without barracks, water or basic hygiene resources. The internees dug holes in the sand to take shelter from the tramontana wind and relieved themselves in the sea. Nonetheless, the camp in Argèles-sur-Mer was not ready to intern so many refugees, hence, not far from this camp, the authorities opened a camp on the coast of Saint-Cyprien and then on the coast of Barcarès. In the three of them, 265,000 refugees were interned, and, in each camp, the challenges were the same: to build a place with electricity, with drinking water, a network of sewers to evacuate wastewater, a functioning postal service, sickness from inhuman conditions and more. By the end of February, the French authorities installed more camps in Bram, in Agde for Catalans, in Septfonds for specialised workers.⁴⁶

⁴⁴ PESCHANSKI, p. 37.

⁴⁵ *Ibid.*, p. 811.

⁴⁶ LAHARIE, p. 33.

As for the deaths in these camps, at the beginning, there were not any specific burial place, the number of deceases could be only known because they happened in the hospital of Saint-Louis de Perpignan. Mainly men deceased at this time because of the injuries and fatigue they got and experienced in the civil war, as well as because of the bad hygiene in the camps that did not allow them to be cured normally even though many solidarity committees intended to help them out.⁴⁷

As far as the coastal camp in Argelès-sur-Mer is concerned, the seashore is over two kilometres long, to the west, they could see the mountain Canigó, the terrain itself was a huge marshland, closed on three sides by a barbed wire fence and on the fourth by the waves of the sea. The land is divided into five *îlots* (a group of houses or buildings), separated from each other by a simple fence. The camp was unprepared in a way that there was no barbed wire to fence off the whole camp or to isolate the *îlots* effectively. The internees often woke up to be covered in rubbish, old papers and clothes that had been blown over by the wind during the night and had piled up around them. Consequently, the inmates started to build themselves wooden barracks. Groups began to be formed in these camps. In Argelès-sur-Mer the most numerous group consisted of Basques with 5000 prisoners. They could even develop their own activities, organise concerts with traditional songs, as well as their own information networks, mail circuits, choirs, discussion groups and cultural gatherings. These internees were young, precisely twenty-six years on average. After a month, the camp was equipped with real barracks and sanitary facilities, which enabled it to resume service until the end of 1941 and even to be transformed into a youth camp under the Vichy regime.⁴⁸ Other coastal camps, like the camp of Saint-Cyprien was closed due to flood.⁴⁹

Claude Laharie details that on 26 February 1939, six internment camps were installed: in Vernet (Ariège) which was a location for the First World War's internment system as well and did not really differ from its predecessor, throughout the two world wars, it had the same purposes: imprisoning the soldiers. Afterwards, they created camp in Rivesaltes (Pyrénées-Orientales) which incarcerated 15,000 refugees that time and in Septfonds (Trarn-et-Garonne) for 16,000 Spanish people with only

⁴⁷ For example, *Junta de auxilio a los republicanos españoles* (JARE) created in France on 31 July 1939, which tried to help Spanish in exile with food and education for children. PESCHANSKI, p. 89.

⁴⁸ LAHARIE, pp. 35–38.

⁴⁹ *Ibid.*, p. 40.

thirty barracks in it. The three other locations were Agde (Hérault), Bram (Aude) and Gurs (Basses-Pyrénées). In Agde, there were 250 wooden barracks and received about 25,000 people, mainly Catalans. The camp of Bram was principally for elderly people and Gurs for Basques, as well as for pilots and mechanics who fought in the air force. This camp, later, would also intern women and children.⁵⁰

When the war was declared in France (3 September 1940), these Spanish refugees would stay in these camps, unless they were men and in good form, then, the French authorities would send them to work (in an unarmed unit of the French army, precisely the *Compagnies de travailleurs étrangers*, in other words the Foreign Workers Companies) or to the French Foreign Legion.

The First Period of Vichy's Camps: The Politic of Exclusion

On 10 July 1940, the French Third Republic collapsed, and the National Assembly voted full powers to Marshal Pétain's government, thus the Vichy regime was established. In social terms, its objective to regenerate French society. From then on, his aim was to create a France which inhabitants are completely French and support the same ideology as he did (he repressed communists, Jews, Tziganes, etc). As a result, he implemented his politic of exclusion conducted by great patriotism which led to the camps' renaissance and the change of their function and characteristics.⁵¹

Between July and October 1940, the Vichy regime introduced a series of decree-laws. The first decree prohibited professional gatherings for Jews and secret societies like for freemasons. Afterwards, the next law applied for those foreigners who had any relation with the French economy, they lost the right to move freely within the country and no longer benefited from employment legislation. The third decree claimed that Jews in the occupied zone were obliged to declare themselves as such at police stations and sub-prefectures. The fourth law ordered that foreign nationals of Jewish race must be interned in camps by the prefects of the departments in which they lived. Therefore, the authorities reopened or continued to use these camps but under the direction of the Ministry of the Interior Affairs and not Defence.⁵²

⁵⁰ Ibid., p. 44–46.

⁵¹ Ibid., pp. 107–108.

⁵² Ibid., pp. 108–111.

In the occupied zone, for the first two years, the German administration was more concerned with ensuring the safety of its troops than with using the internment camps as the main instrument of its repressive policy. The Vichy administration already had a dozen camps. It added around fifteen more during 1941 for politicians, Jews, and Gypsies, which meant that in total, there were around thirty camps. During the regime, several hundred Communists were imprisoned, particularly in Paris and at the Drancy camp, while Gypsies had been persecuted by the occupying forces since the summer of 1940. The Germans obtained the opening of around twenty camps, all small, mainly in the Centre-West of France. Around 1500 Gypsies were imprisoned. The Jews were persecuted later than the Communists and Gypsies, but on a completely different scale.⁵³

The first round-up took place on 13 May 1941 in Paris and led to the arrest of 3710 people. Two other roundups followed in August and December 1941, involving 4975 men and women. They were locked up in the newly opened Drancy camp, then transferred to Compiègne before being deported. All these operations were carried out by the Vichy police at the request of the occupying forces. Regarding the detention conditions, in each camp, the barracks were overcrowded, the heating was insignificant or completely absent, the sanitary facilities were inadequate, and the lack of food often led to malnutrition and stomach diseases. For the first two years, the Vichy regime was keen to assert its power in the occupied zone in the face of the occupier's increasingly demanding supervision.⁵⁴

In the non-occupied zone, by the end of December, there were around 50,000 internees, crowded into the camps, where the slatted walls offered no protection. As a result, during the winter of 1940–1941, there were 693 deaths. In addition, throughout 1941 and until the summer of 1942, the interned population continued to decrease in the camps of France. This drop is mainly explained by the emigration to the United States or Canada, for those who managed to obtain their visas before the winter of 1942; or by the approximately 2000 deaths, often occurring because of the inhumane conditions.⁵⁵ The women's camps in the unoccupied zone are considered small, but their characteristics may seem specific. Rieucros, the first internment camp, then imprisoned around a hundred

⁵³ *Ibid.*, pp. 111–114.

⁵⁴ *Ibid.*, pp. 111–114.

⁵⁵ *Ibid.*, pp. 114–120.

men, most of them were members of the International Brigades. At the start of the war, these first internees were transferred to Vernet, and the centre became camp for foreigners and its function was locking up women and children. This camp consisted of 14 wooden barracks and its capacity of interning was 600 people. These foreigners or undesirables were mainly French communist, alongside with Spanish and German Jewish women and prostitutes. However, most of them were French women who tried to organise multiple activities in the camp for themselves and the children. Thus, the internees could give the children language lessons regularly, many of whom only learnt at that time to read and write. Besides, these women organised activities with authorisation from the administration, such as sewing, shoemaking, canework for chairs and repairing mattresses.⁵⁶

This fragile appearance of life, nevertheless, lasted no longer than when the first deportations began in August 1942.

The Second Period of Vichy's Camps: The Politic of Collaboration and Deportation

With the return of Pierre Laval⁵⁷ on 19 April 1942, France lost its apparent independence, and the collaborationist government became stronger. In November, the Wehrmacht invaded the free zone, southern France also found itself under German control. Laval could offer Germany two things: French labour force and the interned foreign Jews which was also a strategic issue in Vichy's foreign policy.

The pragmatism of the French government became clearer when the French police started to play a major role under the leadership of René Bousquet⁵⁸ who collaborated with Karl Oberg, an SS General and the head of the German police in France. The discussions between them led to the Bousquet-Oberg Agreements of 8–13 August 1942, which based on a dual principle: the French police would receive full autonomy in exchange for full cooperation with the German police. The purposes of the French and German collaboration were mainly fighting against communism, resistance, and to maintain discipline. From this event, the aim

⁵⁶ *Ibid.*, pp. 123–125.

⁵⁷ Pierre Jean Marie Laval was a French politician. During the Third Republic, he served as Prime Minister of France from 1931 to 1932 and from 1935 to 1936. He then occupied the post during the German occupation, from 1942 to 1944.

⁵⁸ René Bousquet was a French political appointee who served as secretary general to the Vichy French police from May 1942 to 31 December 1943.

of the internment camps changed, and began to function more like transit camps to then reach its destination, the Nazis extermination camps.⁵⁹

As a result, at the Berlin conference on 11 June, they agreed to hand over 100,000 Jews to the Germans, besides, the French authorities also accepted that the deportations must be carried out by the French police and gendarmerie, while the task of the Germans was to organise these systematic deportations.⁶⁰

The Jews were first searched in the internment camps, which then ceased to be a safe place for them. Even before the agreements would have been made, Jews were already arrested on 12 December 1941 – when the Wansee conference has not even happened yet –, to be deported from Compiègne to Auschwitz on 27 March. During the period of summer, they began to organise more systematic deportations not only in the occupied, but the non-occupied zones as well, thus, in the third week of June 1942, 10,000 Jews would have been arrested. However, Marshal Pétain intervened to protect those who would have French citizenship whether they were from the north or the south. For now, a compromise was made, hence, only foreign Jews were deported.⁶¹

The north and south had its own internment camps: Drancy, Pithiviers, Beaune-la-Rolande and La Lande internment camps, while in the south, the most numerous and significant were Rivesaltes, Gurs, Noé, Récébédou, Bram and Les Milles internment camps. To give some examples, the two camps, Pithiviers, Beaune-la-Rolande were so-called twin-camps, only twenty kilometres apart from each other. They were both built in 1939 and would intern at that time foreign refugee families from the suburbs of Paris. Both camps interning capacities would be 5000 inmates with wooden barracks. They became Jewish internment camps on 22 April 1941, but the first convoys from each of them would begin to transport the prisoners on 25 June 1942. The only difference between them that from Pithiviers six convoys, while from Beaune-la-Rolande four convoys departed during the summer with in total 8852 men, women, and children. A total of 12,000 were interned in the two camps, including political prisoners from 1943.⁶²

According to Claude Laharie we can also establish a chronology of the deportations. In 1941, there were 320,000 Jews in France, half of

⁵⁹ LAHARIE, pp. 137–138.

⁶⁰ *Ibid.*, p. 139.

⁶¹ *Ibid.*, pp. 139–140.

⁶² *Ibid.*, pp. 141–145.

whom were foreigners. In 1942, nearly 42 000 people were deported to concentration camps and several stages can be clearly identified: after the first six convoys, there were more and more major arrests Paris in mid-July 1942, and in the southern part in August. For example, one of the most significant raids was the raid of “Vel’d’Hiv”, which was a sports facility in Paris, where more than 13,000 arrested foreign Jews were gathered on 16–17 July 1942, including 4000 children. By the end of this summer 32,133 Jews were deported. After that the Germans occupied the southern zone as well, they could not accept the fact that they failed in deporting the Jews with French citizenship, so they proposed the legal deprivation of French citizenship for Jews. After several negotiations, Laval signed the decree on 20 June 1943, according to which the prefects had to hand over the lists of all Jewish residents living in their counties. Therefore, 21,000 Jews were deported from France between September 1943 and August 1944, 11,000 of them in four months (between February and May 1944).⁶³

If we overview these two years of internment camps, in total, 76,000 Jews were deported from France in 77 convoys. Among them, 69,000 Jews were transported to Auschwitz-Birkenau, and approximately 42,000 people lost their lives here. Out of 76,000 deportees, 50,000 were foreign Jews, 26,000 either received French citizenship or were French from foreign parents. By the end of the war, barely 2500 people survived.⁶⁴

The period from the summer of 1942 to the summer of 1944 saw a significant change in the operation and characteristics of the French internment camps, as well as in the lives of Jews of foreign origin and French citizenship. We could observe several turning points, for instance, the collaboration with the German police and the internment camps became transit camps, from here the Jews were transported to the extermination camps.

The Last Steps: Making Exception to Avoid Problems

The history of internment camps in France is a complex and enduring one, stretching far beyond the confines of the Vichy regime and continuing well beyond the Liberation. Even after four years of German occupation and six months of intense repression, internment became a tool of purging during the Liberation period. By October 1944, official records indicated

⁶³ Ibid.

⁶⁴ PESCHANSKI, p. 604.

a staggering 171 camps housing approximately 60,000 internees. The diversity among these populations was striking, ranging from suspected collaborators and nomads interned since October 1940 to black market traffickers and German civilians, many of whom were transferred from combat zones in Alsace, where the mortality rate was alarmingly high.⁶⁵

In the face of such widespread internment, Minister of the Interior Affairs, Adrien Tixier took steps to curb the excesses. He increased inspections of the camps and sought to limit internments and places of detention. Through control commissions, Tixier aimed to differentiate between those unjustly detained and those deserving of imprisonment. The purpose of these camps, according to Tixier, was to shield internees from the spontaneous violence of the population or even local resistance fighters. However, the gendered dimension of the purge became evident in a February 1945 report, which revealed that one-third of internees were women. The plight of certain groups, such as the Gypsies, remained largely ignored, with little attention given to their internment. Even after the regime changed, the legislation regarding internment remained, leaving some, like German civilians, in a state of prolonged uncertainty.⁶⁶

The distribution of internment victims across France from 1938 to 1946 paints a grim picture of the scale of oppression. From the end of the Third Republic to the Liberation, hundreds of thousands were interned, including Spanish, nationals of enemy powers, Jews, politicians, traders, and nomads. Despite the initial estimate of 600,000 internees, the true extent of the suffering endured in France's internment camps may never be fully known.⁶⁷

Conclusion

In our article, we intended to overview, summarise, and compare the History of the concentration and internment camps during the twentieth century. First of all, to clarify the term used for these camps, we aimed to take a look at other countries and cultures imprisoning method and systems. We observed the genesis of these camps, including the Cuban or the Anglo-Boers conflicts, continuing with the Namibian and Francisco Franco's concentration camps, the Laogai and the Soviet Gulag. We could

⁶⁵ Ibid., p. 775.

⁶⁶ Ibid.

⁶⁷ Ibid., p. 811.

discover that each of these camps were created during a conflict, serving as a war strategy for each country and culture.

The French internment camps are no exception from this statement either. With a comparative method, we tried to analyse and examine the reason of using these camps, as well as the functioning, the characteristics and typical traits of individuals incarcerated during the First and Second World Wars. We could see that in each period, the emphasize was on different nations. During the World War I, France aimed foreigners like Austro-Germans, Austro-Hungarians, prostitutes and more importantly men who could be mobilised at that time. Besides, the authorities imprisoned Alsatian-Lorrains with Francophile or Francophobe feelings. However, throughout the World War II, there were more enemies of France. The reason for that might also be the tumultuous of events happening at that time. For instance, the Spanish Civil War had a great influence on the functioning and use of French internment camps, but we shall not ignore either the German impact on the decision of the internment system.

We can conclude undoubtedly that both periods had long-term consequences on each nations mentality and attitude resulting memoirs, autobiographical oeuvres whether published or not, which deserve to be discovered and used as sources in our following research.